

SYNTHETICAL INVESTIGATIONS IN THE CAMPHANE
SERIES. PART V. SYNTHESIS OF ETHYL BICYCLO-
(1:2:2)-HEPTANEDIONE DICARBOXYLATE FROM
ETHYL CYCLOPENTANONE-2:5-
DICARBOXYLATE.

BY P. C. GUHA AND G. D. HAZRA.

The monosodium salt of ethyl *cyclopentanone-2:5*-dicarboxylate has been reacted with one molecule of ethyl bromoacetate to yield *cis*- and *trans*-ethyl 2:5-dicarbethoxy-*cyclopentanone-5*-acetate, which on Dieckmannisation yields a product, containing bicyclo-(1:2:2)-heptanedione-dicarboxylic ester. The latter on hydrolysis and decarboxylation yields bicyclo(1:2:2)-heptanedione carboxylic acid.

Ethyl *cyclopentanone-2:5*-dicarboxylate (I) (*Ber.*, 1936, 69, 1212) was prepared in this laboratory in connection with earlier experiments on synthesis of *northujane* derivatives. The method has been further improved and the yield raised to about double the previous yield. With the improvement effected in the method of preparation, it occurred to us to try whether this substance, with two active hydrogen atoms, could be utilised as a starting material for the synthesis of bicyclic compounds of the *camphane* series.

The mono-sodium derivative of ethyl *cyclopentanone* dicarboxylate (I) reacts with one molecule of ethyl bromoacetate to yield two isomeric forms (*cis* and *trans.*, II) of ethyl 2:5-dicarbethoxy-*cyclopentanone-5*-acetate: (i) b.p. 145-60°/3 mm.; (ii) b.p. 202-30°/3 mm. The lower boiling ester passes over slowly to the higher boiling one during distillation. It has not been possible to establish definitely which of them is *trans* and which *cis*, due to the instability of the corresponding tri-acids formed during hydrolysis, both of the esters giving rise to *cyclopentanone-2*-acetic acid (III). The *cyclopentanone* triester (II) on treatment with sodium in benzene suspension yields a product containing bicyclo-(1:2:2)-heptanedione dicarboxylic ester (IV, R and R₁ = CO₂Et) which could not be isolated from the product of Dieckmannisation, as it could not be distilled undecomposed even under 2 mm. pressure.

(III)

(IV)

The product containing (IV, R and $\text{R}_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) on being boiled with hydrochloric acid (1:4) yields bicyclo-(1:2:2)-heptanedione carboxylic acid (IV, $\text{R}_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{H}$; $\text{R} = \text{H}$). It is interesting to note that Kötzt (*Annalen*, 1900, 350, 229) in his attempt to cyclise ethyl cyclopentanone-2-acetate to the bicyclic compound (IV, R and $\text{R}_1 = \text{H}$) could only obtain the bicyclopentyl-acetone derivative (V, $\text{R} = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$). It is thus clear that Dieckmannisation of (II) to give rise to the bicyclic compound (IV, R and $\text{R}_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) has been possible due to the presence of two more additional carboxy groups

in (II). The isolation of the bicyclic diketo-acid (IV, $\text{R}_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{H}$; $\text{R} = \text{H}$) from (IV, R and $\text{R}_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) on hydrolysis, lends further support to the view that the cyclisation has not proceeded in the direction as observed by Kötzt in which case the compound corresponding to (V, $\text{R} = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) would have yielded a triketo compound (V, $\text{R} = \text{H}$) by complete decarboxylation. The equivalent of the acid (IV, $\text{R} = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{H}$) has been determined and its ethyl and methyl esters as also the semicarbazone of the methyl ester prepared. With a view to obtaining the reduced norbornylene carboxylic acid (VI), the bicyclic diketo-acid (IV, $\text{R} = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{H}$) has been reduced according to the method of Clemmensen to an acid melting at 118° which could not be combusted nor further examined due to the yield being extremely poor.

Work is in progress to convert (IV, $\text{R} = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{H}$) into norbornylene *via* (VI) and experiments on ring-closure of alkyl derivatives of ethyl methylcyclopentanone-dicarboxylate are also contemplated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Improved Method of Preparation of Ethyl cyclopentanone-2:5-dicarboxylate (I).—A mixture of ethyl butane tetracarboxylate (129 g.), molecular sodium (9.6 g.) and dry benzene (500 c.c.) was boiled under reflux for

2 hours. After cooling to 0° , the reaction mixture was acidified with sulphuric acid. The benzene layer after being washed with water was dried and freed from benzene by distillation, the residue distilled under reduced pressure and the fraction b. p. at $139-40^{\circ}/2$ mm. collected, yield 58 g. To ensure proper yield, it is necessary to distil small quantities at a time. The yield of this compound according to the method of Nandi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 279), by the use of sodium ethoxide as the cyclising agent, was 30 g. from 130 g. of ethyl butantetracarboxylate.

Action of Ethyl Bromoacetate on Compound (I): Isolation of Ethyl cyclopentanone-2:5-carbethoxy-5-acetate (II).—The cyclopentanone ester (I, 68.4 g.) was added to molecular sodium (6.9 g.), suspended in dry benzene, when the sodium derivative was mostly formed; towards the end, it was warmed for about 1 hour for completion of the reaction. To the sodium derivative, ethyl bromoacetate (100 g.) was added gradually under shaking. It was allowed to stand for 72 hours at room temperature, then heated on a water-bath for 2 hours when the reaction product became neutral. After cooling it was acidified with 10% sulphuric acid and the benzene layer was freed from the solvent by distillation on a water-bath and the residue subjected to steam distillation. The residue was distilled under reduced pressure and the following fractions separately collected: (i) b.p. up to $135^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 15 g.; (ii) b.p. $135-42^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 8 g.; (iii) b.p. $145-202^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 9 g.; (iv) b. p. $202-30^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 40 g. The residue did not boil at a constant temperature and hence was rejected. The last fraction (iv) on redistillation gave a portion boiling at $202-8^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 35 g. (Found: C, 57.41; H, 8.19. $C_{15}H_{20}O_7$ requires C, 57.32; H, 7.0 per cent). It gives a purple colouration with ferric chloride.

The fraction (iii) on repeated distillation gave an oil, b.p. $202-208^{\circ}/3$ mm. and containing C, 56.69; H, 7.97 per cent. When the preparation of the compound (II) was tried in alcoholic medium, the reaction product was obtained as a gum and could not be purified by distillation. It was also noticed that the use of one molecule of ethyl bromoacetate was not conducive to good yield, some of the cyclopentanone ester (I) remaining unreacted.

The fraction (iii) (4 g.) was heated with 18% hydrochloric acid (40 c.c.) under reflux for 4 hours. After steam distillation, the clear solution was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath when an oily substance was left behind which on being kept at 0° in a vacuum desiccator gave a semi-solid, which completely solidified on being kept on a porous plate in a vacuum desiccator. This crystallised from a mixture of ether and alcohol, m.p. 50° . The ethyl ester was prepared in the usual manner, b.p. $130^{\circ}/18$ mm. The semicarbazone of the ester melted at 174° and was proved to be identical

with the semicarbazone of ethyl *cyclopentanone-2*-acetate, by taking mixed m.p. with a genuine sample. The fraction (iv) on similar treatment gave an acid melting at 50° ; ethyl ester, b.p. $130^{\circ}/18$ mm., giving a semicarbazone, m.p. 174° (Kötz, *Annalen*, 1904, 350, 229).

Cyclisation of Compound (II): Formation of Ethyl Bicyclo-(1:2:2)-heptane-dione-dicarboxylate (IV, R and R₁ = CO₂Et).—A mixture of ester (II, 30 g.; b.p. $202.8^{\circ}/3$ mm.), molecular sodium (2.5 g.) and benzene (200 c.c.) was heated under reflux during 3 hours. After cooling the reaction mixture was acidified with 10% sulphuric acid. The benzene layer after drying was found to decompose on attempting distillation under reduced pressure; hence the product was used as such for the next operation.

Hydrolysis and Decarboxylation of the above Ester: Formation of Bicyclo-(1:2:2)-heptane-dione-carboxylic Acid (IV, R = H; R₁ = CO₂H).—The ester obtained in the foregoing operation was directly hydrolysed with 8% hydrochloric acid by heating under reflux for 12 hours. After extraction of the reaction product with benzene, the acidic solution on evaporation gave rise to (i) a crystalline substance (2 g.), and (ii) a viscous mass. The crystalline product was recrystallised thrice from water, m.p. 212° . (Found: C, 51.8; H, 6.2; Equiv., 189. C₈H₈O₄, H₂O requires C, 51.6; H, 5.4 per cent. Equiv., 186). 0.104 G. of substance lost 0.0074 g. of water at 200° ; hence the substance contains one molecule of water of crystallisation. The viscous mass gave an acidic semicarbazone, m.p. 192° . (Found: N, 20.7. C₈H₁₃O₃N₃ requires N, 21.1 per cent).

Methyl Ester of the Bridged Diketo-acid (IV, R = H; R₁ = CO₂H).—The acid (1 g.) was dissolved in dry ether and a dry ethereal solution of diazomethane was added to it. The ether and the excess of diazomethane was removed under suction. The residual solid crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 129° , yield 0.6 g. Half of it was hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid (1:1), when an acid, m.p. 212° , was obtained, and was proved to be identical with the original acid by mixed m.p. The remaining half of the methyl ester was converted into the semicarbazone which crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. $209-10^{\circ}$ (Found: N, 27.92. C₁₁H₁₆O₄N₆ requires N, 28.3 per cent).

Clemmensen Reduction of Acid (IV, R = H; R₁ = CO₂H).—The acid (1 g.) was reduced according to Clemmensen's method with zinc wool and hydrochloric acid and on being worked up as usual, gave a small quantity of an acid, m.p. 118° . As the amount of this compound was very small its combustion could not be performed.